

The slight deviation of μ_{eff} values (0.15–0.42 B.M.) of the Cr^{III} complexes at 300 K from spin-only value (3.88 B.M.) of octahedral type high-spin Cr^{III} may be due to tetragonal distortion⁶. The μ_{eff} values of the Fe^{III} complexes lie in the range 4.42–4.92 B.M. which are lower than those of a high-spin d^5 ($S=5/2$) configuration (5.83 B.M.) and much higher than those of low-spin ($S=1/2$) configuration (1.73 B.M.).

The three expected spin allowed $d-d$ transitions for an octahedral Cr^{III} ion with ${}^4A_{2g}$ ground state are ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_3)$ with increasing order of energies. Racah and other spectral parameters have been computed in accordance with the procedure adopted by Preti and Tosi⁷. The values of nephelauxetic parameter β (0.70–0.83) and effective nuclear charge Z (1.48–2.08) (Table 2) agree well with those observed in other Cr^{III} complexes derived from N and S donor ligands⁸. The metal-ligand covalency parameter (γ) which is analogous to nephelauxetic parameter is in the range 0.77–0.92 indicating the covalent nature of the complexes. The spin-orbit coupling constant has been calculated from Cole and Garrett's empirical relation: $\lambda = 0.0116(\beta + 1.080)^3 + 0.0062$, which imparts covalent character to metal-ligand bond. The octahedral Fe^{III} complexes exhibit low intensity broad bands in the region 15 380–18 860 cm^{-1} which are due to $d-d$ transitions.

The experimentally measured Mössbauer parameters such as isomer shift (IS) and quadrupole splitting (QS) reveal the geometry of the complexes. The IS values (0.27–0.31 mm s^{-1}) are considerably lower than those observed in typical high-spin octahedral Fe^{III} complexes⁹ (0.4–0.9 mm s^{-1}) but much higher than those of Fe^{III} in the low-spin state (0.04–0.09 mm s^{-1}). Thus the present complexes are regarded as high-spin type possessing spin cross-over properties similar to those reported by other investigators¹⁰ for Fe^{III} complexes. The QS values (0.62–1.04 mm s^{-1}) further suggest distorted Oh symmetry as assumed from electronic spectral data.

Thus the following structure has been tentatively proposed for the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ complexes.

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Studies on Metal Complexes of Thiosemicarbazone and *N*-Phenylthiosemicarbazone derived from 3-Acetylcoumarin

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THIOSEMICARBAZONES and semicarbazones possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties¹. The biological activity of these compounds has often been related to their chelating ability with metal ions². In continuation of our studies on the metal complexes of thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones, we report here the synthesis and characterisation of the Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{I} , Zn^{II} , Pd^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with 3-acetylcoumarin thiosemicarbazone (ACTS) and 3-acetylcoumarin *N*-phenylthiosemicarbazone (ACPTS).

Experimental

All the solvents and the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of ligands: 3-Acetylcoumarin was synthesised as reported earlier³. ACTS and ACPTS were prepared by refluxing for 3 h equimolar quantities of 3-acetylcoumarin and the appropriate thio-

semicarbazide in methanol in presence of a few drops of glacial CH₃COOH. The light yellow ACTS and brick-red ACPTS that separated out on cooling, were filtered, washed with hot water and methanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂. The compounds were recrystallised from methanol and their purity was checked by elemental analyses, mass spectra, tlc and m.p. (ACTS, 196°; ACPTS, 180°).

Preparation of metal complexes : Respective metal acetate salt (except in the case of Fe^{III}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} where chloride salts were used) in methanol or in water-methanol mixture and the ligand solution in methanol in slight excess over 1 : 2 (M : L) ratio, were refluxed on a hot water-bath for 30–60 min. The resulting complex was filtered, washed with hot water and methanol until the washings were free from excess reagent and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂.

The elemental analysis, electrical conductance, magnetic and ir, uv-vis and esr spectral data were obtained as reported earlier⁴. Mössbauer spectrum of Fe^{III}-ACTS was recorded against Fe-foil reference using a constant acceleration ELSCINT drive in conjunction with a multichannel analyser (Promeda); the data were acquired in 512 channels with a mirror image spectrum simultaneously acquired.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable in air at room temperature and insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl no.	Compd *	Found (Calcd.) %		μ_{eff} B.M. (exptl.)
		M	N	
1.	L	—	15.86 (16.06)	—
2.	Fe(L) ₂ Cl ₂	8.74 (8.15)	12.92 (12.27)	5.86
3.	Co(L) ₂ (OAC) ₂	8.01 (8.43)	12.72 (12.01)	5.05
4.	Ni(L) ₂ (OAC) ₂	8.91 (8.39)	12.46 (12.02)	3.23
5.	Cu(L) ₂ (OAC) ₂	8.92 (9.03)	11.43 (11.94)	1.85
6.	Zn(L)(OAC) ₂	14.02 (14.71)	9.84 (9.45)	Diamag.
7.	Pd(L)Cl ₂	23.82 (24.61)	9.10 (9.57)	Diamag.
8.	Cd(L)(OAC) ₂	22.01 (22.87)	8.02 (8.54)	Diamag.
9.	Hg(L)Cl ₂	36.03 (36.61)	8.02 (7.88)	Diamag.
10.	L ₁	—	12.92 (12.46)	—
11.	Fe(L ₁) ₂ Cl ₂	5.98 (6.67)	9.96 (10.04)	5.78
12.	Co(L ₁) ₂ (OAC) ₂	7.01 (6.93)	10.08 (9.86)	4.98
13.	Ni(L ₁) ₂ (OAC) ₂	7.24 (6.90)	10.02 (9.87)	3.16

(Table 1 contd.)

14.	Cu(L ₁) ₂ (OAC) ₂	7.82 (7.43)	10.31 (9.82)	1.82
15.	Zn(L ₁)(OAC) ₂	12.01 (12.56)	7.98 (8.08)	Diamag.
16.	Pd(L ₁)Cl ₂	20.11 (20.68)	8.82 (8.16)	Diamag.
17.	Cd(L ₁)(OAC) ₂	20.40 (19.80)	7.80 (7.40)	Diamag.
18.	Hg(L ₁)Cl ₂	33.01 (32.95)	6.66 (6.89)	Diamag.

*L=ACTS; L₁=ACPTS.

The solutions (10⁻³M DMF) of all the complexes except that of the Fe^{III} complexes show electrical conductance values in the range 8–20 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, indicating their non-ionic nature⁷. This implies that the anions associated with these complexes are present inside the coordination sphere. The Fe^{III} complexes show values around 70 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ characteristic of 1 : 1 electrolyte⁸.

The ir spectrum of ACTS shows two bands around 3 350 and 3 250 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ν_{as} NH₂ and νNH vibrations respectively, and that of ACPTS shows a band around 3 250 cm⁻¹ due to νNH⁶. These bands remain unshifted in the spectra of all the complexes indicating the non-participation of either of the two nitrogens in coordination. The ν_{C=O} band (1 710 cm⁻¹) in the ligands also remains unshifted in the complexes thus ruling out coordination through the oxygen. The ν_{C-S} and ν_{C-N} bands appearing 1 110 and 1 590 cm⁻¹ respectively in the ligands, undergo downward shift in the complexes suggesting that the S and N of these groups are coordinated⁷. The coordination through these groups is further evidenced by ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-N} bands in all the complexes. In addition, all the complexes, except those of Fe^{III}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} show bands around 1 500, 1 450 and 1 350 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to ν_{as}(COO), ν_s(COO) and δ CH₃ vibrations respectively, indicating the presence of acetate ions in the coordination sphere. The Fe^{III}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes reveal ν_{M-Cl} bands around 300 cm⁻¹. Thus both the ligands behave as neutral bidentate ones coordinating through thiocarbonyl sulphur and azomethine nitrogen.

The magnetic and electronic spectral behaviour of all the complexes with both the ligands is the same. The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes show three bands around 8 300, 16 500 and 19 800 cm⁻¹ respectively due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions of high-spin octahedral geometry. The Ni^{II} complexes display three peaks around 8 600, 14 300 and 25 800 cm⁻¹ assigned respectively to the transitions, ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F), ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(P) of octahedral geometry. The μ_{eff} values observed for these complexes confirm the geometry. The Cu^{II} complexes show a single broad band around 18 500 cm⁻¹ suggesting that they are tetragonal⁹. The Fe^{III} complexes show two weak bands around 18 000 and 25 100 cm⁻¹ assigned to spin-forbidden ⁶A_{1g}(S)→

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{ave}	G	K_{\parallel}^2	K_{\perp}^2	λ_0 cm ⁻¹	λ cm ⁻¹
Cu(L) ₂ (OAC) ₂	2.23	2.05	2.17	4.77	0.64	0.53	-828	-526
Cu(L ₁) ₂ (OAC) ₂	2.19	2.04	2.14	4.98	0.52	0.42	-828	-434

⁴T_{1g} (G) and ⁶A_{1g} (S) → ⁴T_{2g} (G) transitions respectively. Based on these results, high-spin octahedral geometry has been proposed for the complexes. The Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and they show two peaks around 15 100 and 17 300 assignable respectively to the transitions, ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} of square-planar geometry. The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are also diamagnetic. These complexes, based on their elemental analysis, conductance and ir spectral data, have been assigned tetrahedral geometry—the most preferred one for them.

The esr parameters calculated for the Cu^{II} complexes are listed in Table 2. There is not much difference between esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature. The complexes show two peaks, one of very low intensity and the other of high intensity, from which g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values have been calculated. The g_{\parallel} values are less than 2.3 indicating covalent character of the metal-ligand bond⁹. The axial symmetry parameter (G) is greater than 4 suggesting no interaction between the copper centres in solid state. The complexes are of out-of-plane π -bonded type since K_{\parallel}^2 values are greater than K_{\perp}^2 values. The spin-orbit coupling constant for the complexes (λ) is less than that for the free metal ion (λ_0), suggesting considerable mixing of ground and excited terms.

The Mössbauer spectrum of Fe^{III}-ACTS shows a moderately resolved six-line pattern with an isomer shift (δ) of 0.58 mm s⁻¹ and a quadrupole splitting (ΔE_q) of 1.66 mm s⁻¹. The δ value observed is in the range reported for high-spin Fe^{III} octahedral complexes¹⁰. The ΔE_q value is, however, higher and this may be due to the lower symmetry of the complex¹⁰.

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Palladium(II) Chloride Complexes of some Aryl Methyl Sulphides. Synthesis and their Electronic Spectral Studies

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THE electronic spectra of the complexes of PdCl₂ with methyl phenyl sulphide and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl methyl sulphides have been studied^{1,2} both in solid state and in solutions and characterised for trans-structure. Molecular orbital diagram for the PdCl₂-(methyl phenyl sulphide)₂ complex has been developed to interpret the most intense bands as electron-transfer transitions. In the present investigation several mono-, di- and trisubstituted phenyl methyl sulphides and their PdCl₂ complexes have been prepared and their electronic spectra have been analysed to study the substituent effects over the charge transfer bands.

Palladium(II) chloride treated with a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was dissolved in water (10 ml). The solution was mixed with the required amount of the ligand in ethanol (70 ml). In all the cases 0.05 mol of PdCl₂ was mixed with 0.1 mol of the ligand. The mixture was then shaken well for a few minutes and left for 1 h; in some cases,

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